

Review Article

Comprehensive Review on Phytochemical Profile, Pharmacological and Nutritional Properties of *Moringa Oleifera* with its Molecular Aspects

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The most extensively grown species of the monogeneric, moringaceae family, is *Moringa oleifera* which is native to south Asia, sometimes known as "The Miracle Tree." The medium-sized agroforestry tree *Moringa oleifera* (Moringaceae) has now naturalized in many other nations. *Moringa oleifera* (drumstick tree, miracle tree) is a nutrient enriched plant that is widely cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions. *Moringa oleifera* is a multi-purpose plant belonging to family Moringaceae. Traditionally, it has been used to cure various types of diseases like diabetes, anaemia, asthma, typhoid fever, arthritis, malaria and skin disease. *Moringa oleifera* is rich in various phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, carotenoids, isothiocyanates, polyphenol, saponins, alkaloid, cardiac glycosides, carbohydrates and glucosinolates. All parts of *Moringa oleifera* including seeds, leaves, roots, flowers, stem, pods have traditional medicinal values. The richness in proteins, vitamins, minerals, and diverse bioactive compounds (flavonoids, glucosinolates, phenolic acids, alkaloids) and in addition, novel isolates such as muramoside A&B and niazimin A&B have been identified in the plant and have various pharmacological effects like potent antioxidant, anticancer, antihypertensive, hepatoprotective, and nutritional effects. The plant has applications in nutrition, medicine, cosmetics, water purification and biofuel. This review synthesizes the findings from multiple recent reviews to present an understanding of its phytochemical profile, pharmacological properties, nutritional properties and effect on various molecular targets.

Keywords: *Moringa oleifera*, Drumstick, Miracle tree, Phytochemicals, Nutrition, Pharmacology, Molecular targets.

INTRODUCTION

Plants are the immediate companions of men. This originates from the story of the world creation as mentioned in the holy books. Man has been using plants for different purposes. The early man, used plants to treat diseases, to make shelter and clothing (Anwar et al., 2007). Plant extract contains phytochemicals like alkaloid, flavonoids, steroids, glycosides and others which are responsible for the various biological activities like anti-microbial antioxidant, anti-cancer, anti-diabetic and other activities. The products derived from several herbs and plants are the source of multifunctional curing agents and are relatively considered as safe for consumption (Pareek et al., 2023). According to the Food and Agriculture

Organization's (FAO) report, 25% of the synthesized drugs are manufactured from medicinal plants. Increased demand for food to tackle hunger and malnutrition problems has been pertinent in developing countries over the last few decades (Azlan et al., 2022). In Asian and African countries, the vast majority of the population suffers from malnutrition because of the deficiency of essential nutrients in foods. It is an affordable and readily available source of major essential nutrients and nutraceuticals and it has the potential to eradicate malnutrition (Rathore & Das, 2022). *Moringa oleifera* belongs to the family Moringaceae, commonly known as the 'drumstick' or 'horseradish' tree. It is known as the "horseradish tree" for its ground root taste and the "drumstick tree" because its pods look like drumsticks when the seeds

are not fully mature. Due to the oil made from the seeds of this plant, it has also been referred to as “ben oil tree” (Keatinge et al., 2017). In some areas, people consume the tender seed pods; fresh leaves are common ingredients in their food because they are rich in nutrients. This plant is commonly referred to as *Moringa oleifera* but is also known by other synonyms such as the “miracle tree” due to its numerous bioactive compounds that attract attention in case of traditional medicine and nutritional circles (Emongor, 2011; Gopalakrishnan et al., 2016). The *Moringa* is often considered as important famine food because of its high resistance to drought conditions owing to their tuberous roots. Almost every part like leaves, fruit, flower, seed of *Moringa* tree is useful for medicinal, functional food preparations, nutraceuticals, water purification and biodiesel production (Gopalakrishnan et al., 2016; Rashid et al., 2008). Various reports show that roots of *Moringa oleifera* have been used as a diuretic, anti-hypertensive, anti-spasmodic, antiulcer, laxative, abortifacient, anti-asthmatic, antibacterial, antifungal and as hepatoprotective agent. *Moringa oleifera* seeds have been used as a coagulant, anti-hypertensive, anti-microbial, anti-spasmodic, anti-inflammatory and for skin and hair care. *Moringa oleifera* flower has been used as hepatoprotective, stimulant, anti-inflammation, anti-tumor and used to reduce cholesterol. The bark also has been used for inflammation, digestive disorders, heart complications, eye diseases and fever. The pod has

been reported for use in diabetes, tonic, anti-helminths, joint pain and tumor (Smith & Lester, 1980). The gum obtained from *Moringa oleifera* has been used in asthma, fever, rheumatoid arthritis and astringent for poultry diet (Matic et al., 2018). The seeds and leaves of *Moringa oleifera* has also been used as feed supplement because of the ability of tree to provide high yield of protein (GUPTA et al., 2012; Jaiswal et al., 2013) (Cáceres et al., 1992; Förster et al., 2015; Klimek-Szczykutowicz et al., 2024; Konucu et al., 2022; Ndabigengesere et al., 1995; Niju et al., 2019; Okuda & Ali, 2019; Pereira et al., 2015; Segwatibe et al., 2023). Despite the advantages, *Moringa* plant contains harmful chemicals, alkaloids and other phytotoxin which have potentially nerve-paralysing properties and other adverse effects when consumed in high doses of the compounds include moringine, moringinine, pectinesterase, phenols including tannin. Recently in Nigeria, *Moringa* has become an outstanding valuable plant that contains carbohydrate, proteins, lipids, vitamin and essential minerals, that have highly beneficial effects to both humans and animals. (Amin et al., 2024; Anwar et al., 2007; Islam et al., 2021)

Parts of the plant and their morphological characteristics

Various parts of the plant *Moringa oleifera* and its morphological characteristics are shown in the **Figure 1**.

Fig 1. Parts of the plant and their morphological characteristics

Taxonomical classification(Mallenakuppe et al., 2019)

Table 1. Taxonomical classification of *Moringa oleifera*

Kingdom	Plantae
Subkingdom	Tracheobionta
Super division	Supermatophyta
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Sub class	Dilleniidae
Order	Capparales
Family	Moringaceae
Genus	Moringa
Species	oleifera

Geographical distribution

Moringaceae is a family of shrubs and trees, which comprise of 13 species that are distributed in the Indian subcontinent (*Moringa oleifera* and *Moringa concanensis*), Kenya (*Moringa longituba* and *Moringa rivae*), northeastern and southwestern Africa (*M. inga stenopetala*), Arabia, and Madagascar (*Moringa drouhardii* and *Moringa hildebrandtii*). *Moringa oleifera* is a tropical deciduous perennial dicotyledonous tree (Stohs & Hartman, 2015). The stem is brittle with a corky, whitish-gray bark, with drooping branches, pale green and bipinnate or more commonly tripinnate leaves (30–60 cm long) with opposite, ovate leaflets. *Moringa Oleifera* which is the native of the sub-Himalayan mountains of northern India; is now cultivated for a variety of purposes in the whole tropical and subtropical regions

of the world. The distribution of *M. oleifera* in the world is outlined in Figure 2. Similarly, different vegetative and reproductive parts of *M. oleifera* tree are shown in Figure 3. (Anwar et al., 2007) It is propagated via cuttings (0.2–1.0 m long), with recommended tree to tree spacing of 1.2 and 5 m between rows to obtain the desirable population of 1666 trees/ha. For foliage production, cuttings are planted with a close spacing to obtain 1 million trees/ha. Propagation through seeds is not recommended because of substantial genetic variation through cross-pollination. The Moringa tree grows best in the temperature range of 25–35 °C under direct sunlight at an altitude of 500 meter and in slightly acidic to alkaline soil (pH 5.0–9.0). *Moringa oleifera* seeds can be planted just after maturity. The tree starts bearing fruits at an age between six and 8 months (Stohs & Hartman, 2015).

Fig 2. The distribution of *Moringa oleifera* in the World. The image was obtained from www.outline-world-map.com.

Fig 3. Different vegetative and reproductive parts of *M. oleifera* tree; i) field grown tree, ii) bundle of foliage, iii) flowers and iv) fruit.

Phytochemical properties:

Moringa oleifera consists of various types of phytochemicals that delivers various medicinal uses. The following table (**Table 2**) describes the various phytochemical classes with phytoconstituents according to its various plant parts (Förster et al., 2015)

Table 2. List of various type of phytoconstituents of various parts of the plant, *Moringa oleifera*

Sl. No.	Plant Parts	Phytochemical class with phytoconstituents	Reference
1	Seeds	i) Phytosterol: β -sitosterol ii) Glucosinolate:4-(α -L-rhamnosyloxy-benzyl) isothiocyanate iii) Glycoside: Glycerol-1-(9-octadecanote), Niazimicin, Niazinin iv) Flavonoid: Quercetin, Kaempferol, Myricetin iv) Alkaloid:O-Ethyl-4-[(α -L-rhamnosyloxy) benzyl] carbamate, Pterygospermin	(M. et al., 2002; Rathore & Das, 2022)
2	Leaves	i) Pterygospermin Glucosinolate:4-(α -L-rhamnosyloxy-benzyl) isothiocyanate, 4- α -L-rhamnopyranosyloxy-benzylglucosinolate, 4-O-glucopyranosyl-caffeoyl quinic acid ((α -L-rhamnosyloxy) benzyl) carbamate ii) Flavonoid: Quercetin, Kaempferol, Apigenin, Daidzein, Epicatechin, Genistein, Isorhamnetin, Luteolin, Myricetin, Rutin, Astragalin, Isorhamnetin, Epicatechin iii) Glycoside: Niazimicin, Niazinin, Oxalates and phytates iv) Vitamin: Vitamin A Vitamin B1- Thiamine Vitamin B2- Riboflavin Vitamin B3- Niacin Vitamin C- Ascorbic acid Vitamin E–Tocopherol v) Lutein Phenolic acids: Caffeic acid, Chlorogenic acid, Ortho - Coumaric acid, Ellagic acid, Para- Coumaric acid, Ferulic acid, Gallic acid, Gentistic acid, Sinapic acid, Syringic acid, Salicylic acid, Cryptochlorogenic acid vi) Alkaloid:4'-hydroxyphenylethanamide- α -Lrhamnopyranoside (Marumoside A), 3''-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl derivatives (Marumoside B), N, α -L-rhamnopyranosyl vincosamide Anthocyanin- Pelargonidin, Delphinidin 3-O-sambubioside	(de Barros et al., 2022; Segwatibe et al., 2023; Sreelatha & Padma, 2009)
3	Stem	i) Glucosinolate:4- α -L-rhamnopyranosyloxy benzylglucosinolate ii) Flavonoid: Quercetin, Procyanidin	(Kumar & Sharma, 2023)
4	Roots	i) Glucosinolate:4- α -L-rhamnopyranosyloxy-benzylglucosinolate, 4-(α -L-rhamnosyloxy-benzyl) isothiocyanate ii) Flavonoid: Quercetin, Kaempferol Procyanidin iii) Alkaloids: Aurantiamide acetat	(Ezeamuzie et al., 1996)
5	Flower	i) Glycoside: Pterygospermin ii) Flavonoids: Delphinidine, Kaempferol	(Kumar & Sharma, 2023)
6	Bark	i) Isothiocyanate, hexadecanoicacidand eugenol ii) Flavonoid: Procyanidin iii) Alkaloid: N-benzyl, S-ethylthioformate	(Kumar & Sharma, 2023)
7	Pod	i) Terpene: All-E-lutein All-E-luteoxanthin, 13-z-Lutein, 15-z- β -Carotene All-E-zeaxanthin ii) Alkaloid: N-benzyl, S-ethylthioformate	(Kumar & Sharma, 2023)

Nutritional and therapeutic values of *Moringa oleifera*

The different parts of the *Moringa oleifera* tree including roots, bark, leaves, flowers, fruits, and seeds are traditionally used in various therapeutic applications including abdominal tumors, hysteria, scurvy, paralysis, helminthic bladder, prostate problems, sores and other skin infections. The therapeutic potential and medicinal properties and the physiological and pharmacological activities of the leaves, seeds, bark, roots and flowers of *Moringa oleifera*. The various safety studies conducted on animals are also reviewed by the authors and they

have concluded that the *Moringa* leaves, flowers and fruit extracts offer a high degree of safety without any adverse effects on humans (Juliani et al., 2010) (Cohen, 2014) (Alegbeleye, 2018; Chukwuebuka, 2015; Jattan et al., 2021; MAKKAR & BECKER, 1997; Thurber & Fahey, 2009; Waterman et al., 2015) The phytochemicals of *M. oleifera* have shown anti-lipidemic, anthelmintic, anti-hyperglycemic, anti-microbial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-proliferative, anti-ulcer, anti-urolithiatic and hepatoprotective properties (Alegbeleye, 2018; Ali Reza et al., 2023; Cao et al., 2022; Fejér et al., 2019; Mohai Ud Din et al., 2025; Shin et al., 2021; Tiloke et al., 2019).

Fig 4. Nutritional and therapeutic values of *Moringa oleifera*

In the following table (Table 3) the biological activity of various parts of *Moringa oleifera* in various extracts with their mechanism of action are shown

Table 3: Biological activity of various parts of *Moringa oleifera* in various extracts with their mechanism of action

Sl. No.	Parts of <i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Type of extract	Type of study	Mechanism of action with their molecular target	Reference
1	Seed	Ethanollic extract	Anti-inflammation study against arthritis	Inflammation causes induction of pro-inflammatory markers Cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6) which show swelling and pain, moringa inhibit pro-inflammatory markers	(Caceres et al., 1991; Cheng et al., 2019; Ezeamuzie et al., 1996; GUPTA et al., 2012; Segwatibe et al.,

		n butanol extraction	Anti-inflammation study for asthma	Inflammation causes induction of pro-inflammatory markers Cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6) which show swelling and pain, moringa inhibit pro-inflammatory markers	2023; Waghmare et al., 2014)
		Aqueous extract	Anti-inflammation study against ulcer colitis	Moringa induced Nrf2-signalling expression which show inhibition of pro-inflammatory markers cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6) and iNOS	
		Moringa seed powder	Antioxidant activity on Spontaneously Hypertensive Rats	Moringa shows antioxidant activity by inhibiting NF- κ B pathway mediated inhibition of iNOS protein.	
		Water and ethanol extract	Anti-inflammatory study	Moringa causes inhibition of pro-inflammatory markers cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6) and iNOS by mediating Nrf-2 pathway	
2	Flower	80% hydroethanolic extract	Anti-inflammation study	NF- κ B activates iNOS, cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6), through NF- κ B pathway which causes inflammation. Moringa shows anti-inflammatory activity by inhibiting NF- κ B pathway which causes inhibition of iNOS and cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6) expression	(Caceres et al., 1991; Ezeamuzie et al., 1996)
3	Leaves	90% hydroethanolic extract	Anti-inflammation study	NF- κ B activates iNOS, cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6), through NF- κ B pathway which causes inflammation. Moringa shows anti-inflammatory activity by inhibiting NF- κ B pathway which causes inhibition of iNOS and cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6) expression and PGE2 expression	(Abro et al., 2025; Al-Asmari et al., 2015; Arabpour et al., 2024; Barhoi et al., 2021; Berkovich et al., 2013; Busani et al., 2011; Caceres et al., 1991; Little et al., 2017; Muniz et al., 2021; Sreelatha & Padma, 2009; Tiloke et al., 2019)
				Inflammation causes induction of pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6) which show swelling and pain. Moringa inhibits these cytokines	
		Hydroalcoholic extract	Hyperlipidaemic study	Moringa inhibits ERK1/2- and JNK-dependent pathways which further inhibits cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-17 and IL-6), CCL117	
		70% ethanolic extract and Aqueous extract	Anti-inflammation study against atopic dermatitis	Inflammation causes induction of pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6) which show swelling and pain. Moringa inhibits these cytokines	

		Anti-inflammatory against wound healing	VEGF expression activates cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6) and COX-2 which show swelling and pain Moringa inhibits VEGF expression which result in reduction of pro-inflammatory marker Cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6) and COX-2
		Anti-inflammation study against in aspirin-induced gastric ulcer rats	Gastric mucosal mRNA expression activates nitric oxide which activates COX and TNF- α which result in inflammation. Moringa shows anti-inflammatory activity by inhibiting gastric mucosal mRNA expression which result in inhibition of COX and TNF- α expression
		To study the effect of Moringa oleifera Gold Nanoparticles in Modulating Oncogenes, Tumour Suppressor Genes, and Caspase-9	Moringa induces apoptosis marker Bax, caspase-3/7 and caspase 9 which inhibits Bcl2 and PARP-1 expression in cancerous cell. Moringa induces apoptosis marker Caspase-3/7 and Caspase 9 which causes cell death
		To study Retinoprotective activity	VEGF overexpression activates PKC- β . Moringa inhibit VEGF expression thus lowers PKC- β and shows retinoprotective effect
		To study antiproliferative activity	Moringa induces apoptosis marker Caspase-3/7 and Caspase 9 which inhibit PARP-1 expression in proliferative cell
		To study Inhibition of cox-2 activity on MCF-7 cell	Moringa show inhibition of NF- κ B, Bcl-2, and PARP-1 expression
		To study anti-inflammatory activity	Moringa inhibit MAPKs and NF- κ B signalling pathways which lowers COX2 expression. NF- κ B signalling pathway activates COX-2 and iNOS expression which result in inflammation. Moringa inhibit NF- κ B signalling pathway and lowers COX-2 and iNOS expression
	Methanol extract	Apoptosis study	Moringa show apoptosis effect by lowering Bcl2 expression and increasing P53, Bax, Cytochrome C
	80% methanol extract	lipid metabolism study	Moringa which improves lipid metabolism

		Petroleum ether extract	Inhibition of Lipogenesis study	Moringa modulates PPAR γ , FAS, C/EBP α , C/EBP β , HSL which causes inhibition of lipogenesis	
		Hot Aqueous extract	To study anti-cancer activity	Moringa causes cleavage of PARP-1 leading to apoptosis	
4	Stem	Ethanol extract	To study anti-inflammatory activity of β -Sitosterol	Moringa inhibits ROS production which decreases cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6) and induces HO-1 enzymes.	(Azlan et al., 2022; Cáceres et al., 1992; Ezeamuzie et al., 1996; Noubissi et al., 2024)
5	Root	Hot aqueous extract	To study anti-inflammatory activity	Inflammation causes induction of pro-inflammatory markers Cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6) which show swelling and pain, moringa inhibit pro-inflammatory markers.	(Ezeamuzie et al., 1996)
6	Fruit	80% Methanol extract	Anti-inflammation study	Moringa supresses activity of NF- κ B activation and reduces NO/iNOS expression.	(Cáceres et al., 1992; Ezeamuzie et al., 1996; Liu et al., 2025; Oguntibeju et al., 2020; Sreelatha & Padma, 2009; Tiloke et al., 2019)
		70% ethanol extract	Apoptosis study	Moringa activates apoptosis through mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPK) activation which causes supersession of ERK and JNK through caspase 9/3 cleavage.	
7	Pod	Deionised hot water extract	Anti-inflammatory study	Moringa inhibits NF- κ B which causes inactivation of inflammation markers Cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6), iNOS and COX 2.	(Cáceres et al., 1992; da Silva Parente et al., 2025; Noubissi et al., 2024; Oguntibeju et al., 2020)
8	Bark	Methanol, petroleum ether and chloroform extract	To investigate analgesic and anti-inflammatory	Moringa inhibits NF- κ B which causes inactivation of inflammation markers Cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6), iNOS and COX 2	(Cáceres et al., 1992; Fornaro et al., 2016; Panelli et al., 2020)
9	Leaves and seed combination	Different extract	To study the Cytotoxicity and apoptosis activity	Moringa represses Bcl2 and thus inhibits SIRT1 which leads to apoptosis.	(Berkovich et al., 2013; Sreelatha et al., 2011; Tiloke et al., 2019)
10	Leaves, Stems and Seeds	Aqueous and ethanol ebioextract	Oxidative Stress, Hyperglycaemia and Kidney Dysfunction in Type 2 Diabetes study	Hyperglycaemia causes ROS overexpression which leads to induction of cytokines, iNOS, COX. Moringa supresses the ROS activation which lead to increase in insulin secretion.	(Banerjee et al., 2014; Cheng et al., 2019; Ghebremichael et al., 2005; GUPTA et al., 2012; Oguntibeju et al., 2020)

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Moringa oleifera has emerged as one of the most versatile plant species with remarkable nutritional and

medicinal significance. The present review demonstrates that the plant is a rich reservoir of bioactive phytochemicals, including flavonoids, glucosinolates, isothiocyanates, phenolic compounds,

alkaloids, vitamins, and essential minerals, distributed across its leaves, seeds, flowers, roots, bark, pods, and stem. In the modern era, moringa has more attention due to their extra-ordinary nutraceutical potential. Moringa is the good source of nutritional and phytochemical compounds, that contribute to a broad-spectrum effect as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antidiabetic, antimicrobial and neuroprotective effects observed in preclinical studies. Advancements in molecular pharmacology have further confirmed that *Moringa oleifera* mediates its therapeutic effects by regulating critical cellular pathways involved in inflammation, oxidative stress, lipid metabolism, apoptosis, and metabolic homeostasis. The modulation of signaling mechanisms such as NF- κ B, Nrf2, MAPK, and PPAR pathways provides strong scientific support to its long-standing use in traditional medicine. In addition, its high nutritional value and ease of cultivation highlight its importance as a functional food capable of addressing micronutrient deficiencies and malnutrition, especially in resource-limited regions. Collectively, these attributes position *Moringa oleifera* as a promising natural source for health promotion and disease prevention.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

Despite strong experimental evidence that *Moringa oleifera* has therapeutic potential, there is still little clinical application of this plant. In order to confirm its pharmacological efficacy, safety profile, and dosage standardization, future research should give priority to controlled human clinical trials. Developing plant-based medicines will require the isolation and characterization of active ingredients as well as thorough mechanistic investigations at the genomic and proteomic levels. New avenues for improving the clinical efficacy of compounds derived from moringa include nano-formulation, targeted drug delivery, and bioavailability enhancement. To guarantee safe consumption, thorough toxicological evaluations are also necessary, especially in cases of prolonged use or high-dose exposure. The plant has great potential for the creation of nutraceuticals, functional foods, cosmetics, water purification systems, and renewable bioenergy products in addition to its medical uses. *Moringa oleifera* has the potential to develop into a widely recognized natural

resource for sustainable nutrition and healthcare with integrated scientific validation and regulatory support. Flavonoids of these edible flowers offer diverse potential health benefits and valuable medicinal applications. Exploring of flavonoids of edible flowers represents the area of future research. The edible flowers are rich of various flavonoids. Future aspects will focus on conducting the large scales clinical trials of therapeutic potential on various chronic diseases like cancer, diabetes, neurodegenerative diseases, cardiovascular disease. These strategies aim to state phyto-chemicals' activity as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and antimicrobial agents that help to combat conditions ranging from viral infections to drug-resistant bacteria and age-related decline. Future aspects can reveal the anti-proliferation potential of its phyto-chemicals and improve the antibiotic efficacy against drug-resistant bacteria.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The authors gratefully acknowledge the Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Guru Nanak Institute of Pharmaceutical Science and Technology, Kolkata, for academic support and research encouragement. The constructive comments and discussions from colleagues greatly helped improve the quality of this review article.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no competing financial interests or personal relationships that could influence the work reported in this manuscript

Author contributions: AS conceptualised the review and prepared the original draft. SS and SH contributed to the literature analysis and data compilation. BR and ND supervised the study and critically revised the manuscript. All authors approved the final version.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement: All data analysed in this study are included in the article and its referenced sources.

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Cite: Akash Sarkar*, Sudipta Santra, Sakasi Halder, Nilanjana Das, Babul Raj, Comprehensive Review on Phytochemical Profile, Pharmacological and Nutritional Properties of *Moringa Oleifera* with its Molecular Aspects, *Int. J. Med. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (5), 417–430. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20097262>